

THE “EDUCATION→ENGINEERING←ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE” PARADIGM OF PUBLIC ACTIVITY IN THE “TECHNO-DEMOCRATIC-INFORMATION SOCIETY”

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Abstract

The research shows that intellectual and creative activity of everyone living in the "Techno-democratic-information society" becomes a paramount requirement, and for this, it is desirable for every member of this society to rise to the level of a subject of intellectual skills, they must have information culture and technological literacy.

The research work clarifies the main reasons for the reforms carried out in the education system and its implementation system in connection with the challenges of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, and expresses the attitude towards the logic of the existence of subsystems such as STEM and STEAM (active/interactive or learner-centered) education, based on the paradigm of "education→engineering←artificial intelligence" of social activity in the "Techno-democratic-information society" and the schematic description of the path of implementation expressed as "S-S".

Finally, this work highlights the irreplaceable importance of artificial intelligence in the context of the Fourth Industrial Revolution and digital technology, and considers artificial intelligence as a strategic technology central to Industry 4.0; It is emphasized that the impact of artificial intelligence on the future will depend on how we manage the technology and how we adapt to this change as a society, and a concise explanation of the rather wide range of its engineering applications is given.

Keywords: Education; Technology; Information society; Information culture; Technological literacy; Artificial intelligence; Engineering applications; Paradigm of social activity.

Introduction

Everyone living in the currently formed "Techno-democratic-information society" must perform intellectual, creative activities. For this, a person must rise to the level of a subject of intellectual skills. The importance of artificial intelligence in the context of the IV industrial revolution and digital technology is irreplaceable. Artificial intelligence is selected as a strategic technology that occupies a central place in Industry 4.0.— The impact of artificial intelligence on society, education, health and quality of life, social interaction and social behavior, changing the economic structure, ethical and legal issues, human-machine collaboration, data-driven learning and prediction systems, deep learning - a branch of machine learning, the use of multilayer artificial neural networks, and so on seems logical.

The impact of artificial intelligence on the future will depend on how we manage technology and how we adapt to this change as a society. It is undeniable that education has an important role in preparing society for this process, and from the point of view of the realization of the aforementioned preparation, a learner-centered system based on the “education → social activity ← artificial intelligence” paradigm should take its place as a superstructure phenomenon, and the theoretical and technological foundations of the optimal ways of realizing such a system should be clear. This problem makes the solution of cognitive issues formed by focusing on various types of social activity relevant. “Determining the nature of education based on the “education → engineering ← artificial intelligence” para-

digm of social activity in a techno-democratic-information society” has a special place among the cognitive issues that need to be solved.

Purpose of the study: The aim is to determine the directions for defining the nature of education within the “techno-democratic-information society,” based on the paradigm of “education → engineering ← artificial intelligence.” In this context, it is taken into account that the idea itself represents a fundamental value; the human world of activity has always been grounded in ideas; and every individual advances step by step by verifying the adequacy of their actions with the idea they consider acceptable as the outcome of their activity.

Methodological basis of the research: In the process of conducting the research, L. Bertalanfi's "Idea of System Analysis" [3;8] was used (the idea, which is interpreted as an attempt to study the properties of an object based on the properties of its parts - italics are ours - F.I.; S.I.; G.A.) The "System-structural approach", which has been formed as an important branch of dialectics and has risen to the level of its alternative, empirical, empirical-theoretical and theoretical methods of scientific cognition, the internal relationships of the forms of scientific cognition, and various pedagogical and psychological research generalizations were used as a methodological basis.

Interpretation of generalizations from research materials: Throughout history, radical changes in industry and production processes have been described as industrial revolutions. These revolutions have significantly transformed production methods, the structure of the workforce, and the social system through technological advancements.

The First Industrial Revolution (late 18th and early 19th centuries) was characterized by the discovery of steam power and the use of mechanical production machinery. During this period, the mechanization of textile and metallurgical production led to a significant increase in production capacity and accelerated the migration of rural communities to industrial areas. The use of mechanical power reduced the complexity of production and created the basis for mass production.

The Second Industrial Revolution (late 19th century–early 21st century) was defined by electricity, steelmaking, and mass production technologies. The distribution of electricity enabled continuous production lines in factories and standardized "production lines" (flows). Henry Ford's assembly lines enabled mass production and ultimately reduced production costs. During this period, engineering practices, production management, and organizational structures achieved a certain degree of modernity.

The third industrial revolution (dating back to the mid-20th century) was characterized by the rise of computers, electronic devices, and automation technologies. Computer-aided design (CAD), robotic production lines, and control systems increased the efficiency of production processes and reduced human intervention. During this period, information technology, data processing, and automated control systems enabled faster and more accurate results in engineering and scientific research. Industry 3.0 also helped to make production and logistics networks more integrated and flexible on a global scale.

The current fourth industrial revolution (Industry 4.0) is characterized as an era of integration of physical, digital and biological systems. The Fourth Industrial Revolution has different implications for different areas of our lives. The Fourth Industrial Revolution requires the simultaneous and comprehensive use of technologies such as cyber-physical systems, the Internet of Things (IoT), big data analytics, cloud computing and artificial intelligence. Industry 4.0 is changing not only production processes, but also scientific research methods, economic structures and public order.

This stage of development has created new opportunities for education that bring values specific to civilization (the use of different technologies such as IoT, 3D printing, quantum computing, artificial intelligence, etc. has led to a more effective transfer of information)[20; 78-94].

As can be seen, the process of civilization has been continuously formed in response to the calls of the "Industrial Revolutions", systems of socio-economic relations have been established on the basis of dialectical conditioning of one another (logical expectation), and superstructures based on the aforementioned bases have been formed. Currently, there is a system-basis such as the "technodemocratic information society" that makes people stronger.

"Information society" means the production and use of information, information resources, basic technologies and techniques of the information society, new information - telecommunication technologies and techniques, etc. The main characteristic features of the information society are: meeting the mass information needs of society; information economy in society; high

level of information demand of society members; high information culture in society, expansion of open information networks for society members; prospects for the formation and development of a single information environment; information security for society members; level of globalization and integration, etc. In general, the provision of all members with sufficient information in an appropriate manner and the implementation of information services at a high level are the specific features of the society in question. The information society, unlike the industrial society, is a more intellectual society and creates conditions for the highly educated, skilled, determined, and comprehensive development of people.

The main features of the "Technodemocratic information society" established in the modern world suggest that the people represented in this society must have information culture and technological literacy, otherwise they will not be able to assert themselves as active and creative members of the society in question.

By the way, let us note that in the concept of "Information culture" we mean the acquisition of a system of knowledge, intellectual skills and habits necessary for a person to adapt to the information society. It is undeniable that the role of the computer network in the formation of information culture is great. Information culture: is the ability to use information resources and information communication tools of society; is the application of advanced achievements in the field of informatization and the development of information technology tools in society; is the ability to obtain and transmit information using modern technical means and methods, computer technologies.

Technological literacy– the ability of people to use various digital technologies, analyze data, and operate safely in a digital environment. "This skill is not limited to using a computer and the internet, but also includes: 1) Adhering to digital safety and cybersecurity rules; 2) Working with artificial intelligence and automation; 3) Digital analytics and data processing skills; 4) Using cloud technologies; 5) Quickly adapting to new technologies"[9] Technological literacy includes the ability to use information and communication technologies.

Modern education, which is currently establishedIt is one of the superstructures of the existing base as a "technodemocratic information society". It is undeniable that education, which is a process of sharing human experience, has developed in stages as a product of social practice (and especially pedagogical science), incorporating the characteristics of industrial revolutions. In the era of the IV industrial revolution, an education system that can form a creative, innovative and globally competitive generation is required, and currently the impact of the aforementioned revolution on the educational process, the issue of "education of the future" is being discussed on various platforms and the necessary steps are being taken accordingly.[17], [18; 92-97].– –

Digital education, improves people's ability to participate independently in modern social life. In addition, the reality of digital education and the digital revolution requires fundamental changes in the forms

and methods of moral education, leading to the emergence of digital skills as the most important competence [22;58-64]. The development of digital skills is essential to ensure that they can safely and effectively interact with digital technologies in the future. Education systems need to take a comprehensive and integrated approach, supporting all learners to develop the skills to be active and ethical users of digital technologies. [23; 57-79]

It is necessary to distinguish two main reasons for the reforms carried out in the education system and its implementation system in connection with the challenges of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. The first is the training of a workforce with knowledge (information) and skills in accordance with the needs of a rapidly changing global economy, and the second is the establishment of an education and implementation system that can bring to the fore the productive forces (labor force) necessary for the development of an adequate information society during the industrial revolution. [15;288]

Despite what has been said, the basis of public activity in the "Technodemocratic information society" is "education".—→engineering artificial intelligence" paradigm is set and←The schematic description of the implementation path is that education, expressed as "SS" (active/interactive or learner-centered), has subsystems such as STEM and STEAM.

The STEM subsystem has been applied in the education system of a number of countries since the second half of the last century. In this system, mathematics, technology, engineering and natural sciences are implemented in interaction (together). The main goal of the application of STEM is to form and develop "XXI century 4C skills" in schoolchildren. The inclusion of the aforementioned system in education creates such a dominant environment that schoolchildren develop their creativity, teamwork skills, logical thinking, and problem-solving skills by applying the various information they learn in mathematics and natural sciences to various problems they encounter in their daily lives and in various projects. [2;22-23] It is undeniable that Creativity is considered the most basic skill that distinguishes humans from other living beings, and the application of STEM creates conditions for developing creative skills in learners during teaching. Learners who participate in the process that includes this system as the main party have the opportunity to observe the results obtained during small-scale experiments, investigate the errors that arise, and rebuild the experiments. It is precisely in such an organized environment that the information obtained is more permanent, since the learning process is based on discussion in the form of groups, learners express their attitude to the work of their teammates, justify their arguments. The organizational form chosen adequately for the process that includes STEM usually ends with a report or presentation on the results of the experiment or project. Since the process that includes STEM is more project-based and organized in a group work format, group members also perform a leadership function, lead the group/project, and make decisions. As a result, leadership skills are developed in learners. The main goal of the training

process that transforms STEM as a subsystem is to prepare students for the future work environment. All of the skills mentioned above prepare students for positions they will hold as effective human resources. [13]

Included in the active/interactive learning process Although the STEAM subsystem differs from STEM in only one direction - A-Art (art), the advantages of training based on the STEAM model are great. Thus, this system: 1. Stimulates creative thinking; 2. Offers meaningful collaboration; 3. Strengthens critical thinking; 4. Provides a unique way to solve problems (students are forced to use methods that lead to unusual solutions to solve existing problems); 5. Provides practical learning experience.

The process involving STEAM is more creative and fun. Based on logical grounds, it can be hoped that learners who are influenced by the cognitive or technological process involving this subsystem will be able to apply innovations in the future. In the process of this nature, they use various fields: mathematics and other exact sciences, engineering, design, digital devices and technologies. STEAM is a system with a universal practical orientation, relatively independent or dominant, allowing students to perform any complex task, in which students put their knowledge into practice. The cognitive or technological process that includes this subsystem is useful and necessary for every modern school. The unique place of STEAM in the educational substrate provides students with the opportunity to learn creatively using 21st century skills such as problem solving. It is worth emphasizing that "The 4C skills of the 21st century are collaboration, creativity, critical thinking, and communication. They are essential components of individual success in a rapidly changing workforce and society." [12]

The transformative process of STEAM is to integrate subjects into a unified learning model based on real-world applications, rather than teaching them in isolation. ThisIt is an integrated "enabler" of learning that requires a connection between standards, assessments, and lesson design/implementation, andIt produces results in terms of positive self-denial in students who take deliberate risks, engage in experiential learning, persist in problem solving, embrace collaboration, and work in a creative process: these are the innovators, educators, leaders, and learners of the 21st century!

Based on scientific research, we conclude that those who are educated in a "sharing process" based on the combination of Science, Technology, Engineering, Art, and Mathematics will contribute to development by shaping themselves as creative, innovative, and enterprising individuals of the future with special abilities and talents.[6]

The application of this system of implementing education leads learners to the following conclusion: Science helps people understand the laws of the world; engineering and technology help people change the world according to social needs; art helps people enrich the world in a good way; and mathematics gives people the structural analysis to develop and apply the methods and analysis tools of science, engineering, art, and technology.

It must be concluded that the process in question is related to the "why and how", it is a process of application, a system that allows for the creation of meaning. Here, the idea is based on research, a critical approach, and deep questioning.[7]

In the system that includes STEAM, project-based learning (PBL), interdisciplinary integration and cross-disciplinary learning, inquiry-based learning, design-based learning, game-based learning, analogy-based learning, mobile-based learning, and making small changes, making-doing learning methods are used more. 3D design modeling (Tinkercad), 3D printing, block programming on the micro bit platform, and implementing projects with sensors (Coding) are the main tools that are important during the project.—[6].

In this system Basically, project-based learning, problem-based learning as the main teaching (learning) approach, aims to guide learners through cooperation and experience, complete the subject of the project, and solve problems encountered in life. As a kind of traditional education mode, the STEAM substrate system has the potential to reduce the gap between students' existing knowledge and skills and professional knowledge and skills and increase their competitiveness.

Digital technologies, becoming a part of our lives, are bringing both structural and power changes to the education system. Today, people with strong disciplinary knowledge, analytical, creative and critical thinking skills are in demand in all fields. Based on logic, one can believe in the effectiveness of the knowledge and skills that this system provides to learners, their professional development and future life.[4;145]

Education that includes STEAM can help students enrich their learning experiences at a lower cost, which is essential for students to succeed in a rapidly changing world, and it teaches students to evaluate their personal interests, life opportunities and career development, current and potential contexts, and to understand the future of their careers, professional interests and develop their knowledge and skills well. Students who are covered by education based on the mentioned system and teachers who have an organizational and management function and facilitate this process build more real-life relationships. This is desirable. Because school is not a place where students go simply to learn. Students should have the following conclusion: "We are always learning, we are always growing, we are always experimenting."

In order for students to demonstrate their skills and abilities in new areas emerging under the influence of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, it is necessary to implement fundamental changes in technology and the curricula of the subjects taught. By reviewing the curricula of the subjects formed on the basis of chemistry, biology, physics, etc., which are considered "basic sciences" in the new curricula, more attention should be paid to the teaching of computer science subjects, which play a key role in the formation of the Fourth Industrial Revolution literacy. Naturally, more attention should be paid to the teaching of the subjects in question. [26; 432-466]

Due to the rapid development of technology, the knowledge and skills that students learn during their education become obsolete by the time they graduate. In order to help develop and shape the use of today's fastest-growing technologies in scientific and technical education, it is necessary to educate students and prepare them for the digital environment. Adapting to a rapidly changing environment requires that students maintain contact with educational institutions even after graduation. and will provide both workers with updated skills and young learners (and faculty) with a new direction relevant to the rapidly changing realities of the industrial and corporate sectors.[24; 25-30], [25; 579-592]

It is undeniable that there is a specificity in the calls of each industrial revolution. This is manifested against the background of global changes taking place in the world, and at the same time it determines the existence of new shades in information culture and in the content of technological literacy. At different stages of world history, humanity has faced serious changes and achieved results with the reforms carried out. Against the background of industrial revolutions, educational program developers had to seek answers to the following fundamental questions: 1) What knowledge, skills and values should be reflected in educational programs?; 2) Will these knowledge, skills, values and competencies form the necessary life skills in learners?; 3) How can the process of implementing education be made relevant and interesting for learners?; 4) How can assessment (an integral part of the process of implementing education) be made more productive and effective?

In our modern era, parameters such as relevance, practicality, effectiveness, and sustainability are the indicators of the quality of an educational program, while the indicators of its success are the quality of acquisition by learners and the extent to which learners can effectively use what they have acquired for their personal, social, cognitive, psychological, and emotional development. [5; 5]

By the way, UNESCO has the following criteria for a quality education program. An education program should: have clear objectives; meet today's requirements; be relevant to the current and future lives, experiences, desires and aspirations of learners; aim to build a prosperous future for learners in social and economic terms, taking into account the history and culture of the country in which they live; be fair and inclusive (taking into account the individuality, individual needs of learners, etc.); be learner-centered (takes into account the needs of the learner, is appropriate to the learner's age, helps in personal development and the formation of life skills, and does not overload learners); be open and flexible (integrates emerging innovations into the content); be consistent and relevant.[5; 5]

The Fourth Industrial Revolution has had an impact on the education system as well as on the socio-economic spheres. In line with the industrial revolutions, "education, which is a process of sharing the experience of understanding and transformation", has developed in stages (including the specific characteristics of industrial revolutions). It is worth emphasizing that the expected paradigmatic changes in the education

system and the implementation of global education reform have been further accelerated by the influence of the Fourth Industrial Revolution[27; 147-171].

In connection with Industry 4.0, we would not be wrong to say that “innovation has begun to dominate education systems”. In our opinion, educational institutions will have to see innovation not only as a means of ensuring increased global competitiveness under the influence of globalization, but also as one of the main parts of the education system. In accordance with the requirements of the times, the teaching of new technologies will be accepted as one of the main needs on a logical basis. “Lifelong learning” will be the main motto of the education system. Naturally, the content of education should also take into account the skills of the 21st century: in addition to knowledge, the development of abilities and skills such as complex problem solving, critical thinking, creativity, leadership, digital literacy, emotional intelligence, global citizenship, cooperation, discussion, judgment and decision-making will also be accepted as the main learning outcomes.

Education 4.0 should serve to form the skills (intellectual skills) to use new technologies that help learners develop in accordance with changes in society. It should form knowledge and skills that learners can use throughout their lives, not just reading and writing. Thus, the system should respond to changes in the social and economic environment to meet the needs of human capital. Education 4.0 aims to prepare individuals to be creative and innovative. Education should adapt to the environment in which learners live and provide them with a secure and successful future. This new system uses “smart” school management systems, learning management programs, communication tools, and teaching and learning tools.[19; 238-254]

In the Education 4.0 approach, going beyond constructivist education systems and Bloom's taxonomy, intellectual It has been determined that an environment-based learning process will be applied that focuses on the formation and development of skills: 1) 3Rs (Recalling, Relating, Refining) that regulate understanding; 2) 3I (Inquiring, Interacting, Interpreting) that encourages research; 3) 3Ps (Participating, Processing, Presenting) that are based on drawing conclusions.[28; 92-98], [29; 40-45]

Education 4.0, which provides an effective environment for the formation of intellectual skills, has the following characteristics: 1) Learning regardless of time and place (lifelong learning, e-learning, etc.); 2) The opportunity to receive personalized education according to the skills and abilities of students; 3) Taking into account the suggestions of students when preparing the curriculum; 4) Predominance of project-based learning; 5) Formation of students' ability to conduct analysis on large-scale data (Big Data); 6) Assessment of students' knowledge in the process of applying them to projects; 7) Becoming a part of the educational system of emerging new technologies, etc. [17-18]

In the era of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, "smart" educational tools and resources should enable individuals to acquire more advanced experience, knowledge, and skills, and to reveal their innovative perspectives.

In the context of the fourth industrial revolution and digital technology, the importance of artificial intelligence is irreplaceable. Artificial intelligence is highlighted as a strategic technology that occupies a central place in Industry 4.0. Big data and machine learning algorithms allow for immediate analysis of data on production lines, prediction of possible failures and automation of decision-making processes. This provides a decisive advantage, especially for smart factories, autonomous logistics systems and special production models. Smart grids in the electricity and energy industry; On the other hand, production planning, logistics management and process optimization in industrial engineering are becoming more effective thanks to artificial intelligence-based solutions.

■ Artificial intelligence has a fairly wide range of applications in engineering. In mechanical engineering, artificial intelligence is widely used for optimizing production processes, predicting failures and maintenance, and controlling robotic systems. It is worth emphasizing that:

* Prediction: Equipment failures are predicted in advance using sensor data and machine learning algorithms. This reduces production downtime and reduces maintenance costs.

* Robotics and automation: Artificial intelligence algorithms in autonomous robotic systems improve motion planning, task optimization, and human-robot interaction.

* Design optimization: Artificial intelligence allows you to find efficient solutions by using complex engineering in modeling and optimization processes.

■ Electrical and electronics greatly benefit from the application of artificial intelligence in energy management, circuits, and smart systems.

■ Smart Grids: AI optimizes electricity generation and distribution, providing demand forecasting and fault detection.

■ Unattended systems: electric cars, drones, and other autonomous devices can perform perimeter sensing, route optimization, and safe navigation thanks to artificial intelligence algorithms.

■ Circuit and system design: Performance analysis and electronic circuit optimization can be performed with machine learning, shortening design time.

■ Artificial intelligence is used in engineering to monitor the condition of buildings, analyze risks, and develop sustainable projects.

■ Structural health monitoring: sensor data is analyzed using machine learning algorithms to determine the longevity of the structure and possible damage.

■ Risk analysis and disaster management: artificial intelligence models help to secure building structures by predicting the risks of earthquakes, floods, and other natural disasters.

■ Smart city applications: urban life is optimized using artificial intelligence-based systems for traffic management, energy efficiency, and infrastructure planning.

■ Industrial engineering actively uses artificial intelligence in planning production processes, managing logistics, and optimizing processes.

* Production planning: Artificial intelligence algorithms allow for optimal decisions in raw material supply, production lines, and workforce planning in July.

* Logistics and supply chain management: inventory optimization, route planning, and distribution processes become more efficient with machine learning.

* Process optimization: the efficiency of production and operational processes increases, costs are reduced, and product quality is improved.

The use of artificial intelligence in engineering not only increases the efficiency of production and design processes, but also enhances the creative and analytical thinking abilities of engineers. In addition, thanks to interdisciplinary integration, artificial intelligence allows developing innovative solutions in various engineering fields. In this context, artificial intelligence is positioned as an integral part of modern engineering.

There is no denying that artificial intelligence is playing an increasingly important role in scientific research and engineering, and this is an ongoing process. Complex data sets, experimental modeling, and interdisciplinary research are becoming faster, more accurate, and more efficient thanks to artificial intelligence algorithms.

In general, the impact of AI on the future will depend on how we manage the technology and how we adapt to this change as a society. In our opinion, it seems logical that AI will have an impact on society, education, health and quality of life, social interaction and social behavior, changing economic structures, ethical and legal issues, human-machine collaboration, data-driven learning and prediction systems, deep learning - a branch of machine learning, the use of multilayer artificial neural networks, and so on.

It can be said that artificial intelligence is based on mathematical modeling, data analysis, and algorithmic learning. Machine learning, deep learning, and data-driven models allow for the effective use of artificial intelligence in modern engineering and scientific research. We believe that these are the necessary infrastructure for the transition to engineering and scientific applications.

Scientific novelty of the research: The idea of education based on the paradigm of "education → engineering ← artificial intelligence" of social activity in the "techno-democratic-information society" has been brought to the attention of the scientific community.

The theoretical significance of the study: "This research has a specific function in line with the call to direct further scientific and scientific-pedagogical activity on a broad study of theoretical and practical ways to solve the problem of "creating conditions for sustainability for the future development of society."

Practical Significance of the Study: The practical significance of the study lies in the fact that, in real pedagogical practice, practitioners have gained the opportunity to utilize the idea of education based on the paradigm of societal activity in the "techno-democratic-information society" as "education → engineering ← artificial intelligence" in their professional activities.

Conclusion:

1. In the "techno-democratic-information society," it becomes a priority requirement for every individual to engage in intellectual and creative activities, and for this, it is necessary for each member of this society to reach the level of a subject of intellectual skills.

2. In a society formed in accordance with the challenges of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, it is a desirable quality for each member to possess information literacy and technological competence.

3. The education system adequate to the "techno-democratic-information society" has found its place in scientific literature and pedagogical practice under the term "Education 4.0" and has been interpreted as a higher-level structure based on logical principles.

4. "Education 4.0," which provides an effective environment for the formation of intellectual skills, has specific characteristics.

5. The study has determined ideas regarding the directions for defining the nature of education based on the paradigm of societal activity in the "techno-democratic-information society" as "education → engineering ← artificial intelligence."

6. In the context of the Fourth Industrial Revolution and digital technology, the significance of artificial intelligence is indispensable; artificial intelligence is selected as a strategic technology occupying a central position in Industry 4.0.

7. The impact of artificial intelligence on the future will depend on how we manage technology and how society as a whole adapts to this change.

8. The use of artificial intelligence in the field of engineering not only increases the efficiency of production and design processes but also enhances the creative and analytical thinking capabilities of engineers.

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